

Aalto University

CS-C3240 – Machine Learning

Evaluating Machine Learning Models for Short-Term Bitcoin Price Forecasting

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1 Introduction

In recent years the importance of various cryptocurrencies has grown significantly in the world economy. Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies, are of particular interest, because their value is not linked to any real world financial agent or -asset. The value of various financial instruments, especially cryptocurrencies, are known to be extremely hard to predict; often fluctuation over a short time period are seemingly random. However, many micro- and macroeconomic indicators that correlate with price development in the global asset market can be observed, which lays the foundation for this machine learning problem. This project aims to explore correlations between Bitcoin’s value and the price trends of stock indexes using machine learning, and assess the potential for predicting Bitcoin’s future value.

This report explains the application of machine learning with the described problem and clarifies the data used for training and testing the machine learning model. The specific machine learning models and loss functions that will be used in the project will also be discussed.

2 Problem formulation

In this project, supervised machine learning methods are used to find a regression function that attempts to describe a correlation between the future value of Bitcoin (in USD) and the previous values of Bitcoin and the Nasdaq composite index (NASDAQ COMP). The application of the function is to predict the value of Bitcoin one day ahead of time, using metrics from both Nasdaq composite and Bitcoin as input variables.

The used model applies continuous numerical data of the value of Bitcoin and the Nasdaq composite index as features. The model is trained with the following features for each label:

	B_o	B_{max}	B_{min}	B_v	B_{d3}	B_{dw}	N_o	N_c	N_{max}	N_{min}	N_{d3}	N_{dw}	=>	L
Date	Data 1	Data 2	Data 3	Data 4	Data 5	Data 6	Data 7	Data 8	Data 9	Data 10	Data 11	Data 12	=>	Label

Table 1: Features assigned to a label

Table 1 describes the features assigned to each label, where: B_o and N_o are the values at the starting of the day (00:00) (for Nasdaq the opening value), B_{max}, N_{max} and B_{min}, N_{min} are the maximum and minimum values during the day, B_{d3} and N_{d3} are the value changes in the last three days, and B_{dw}, N_{dw} are the change during the week for both Bitcoin and Nasdaq composite index. For Bitcoin, we used values recorded at 00:00, while the Nasdaq COMP opening values were selected for analysis. These features were chosen for their relevance to recent market behavior and ease of calculation. The model focuses on short-term predictions, incorporating only the most recent data.

The label for which the data will be trained on, is the highest value of the day for Bitcoin one day in to the future from the feature data used.

The data for Bitcoin was found from Kaggle as Bitcoin Historical Dataset [1], and it contains daily data from 2014-2022. The data for Nasdaq was found from Nasdaq’s website[2], which contains data from 2014-2024. Both are in .CSV-file format.

3 Methods

The dataset for this project was formed from two different sources and trimmed to include only the same time period. The US stock market (which the Nasdaq COMP follows) is closed on Saturdays, Sundays and some holidays, so these days were missing from the Nasdaq data. In our simplistic model, the COMP index for the missing days was considered to be the same as the closing COMP index from the last open day.

Four of the feature values were processed from the data by calculating the changes in BTC valuation and Nasdaq COMP in the last three days and in the last week. To form the rest feature values, the first 7 elements as well as the last element was cut from the dataset. The label values were then formed by dropping the first 8 elements from the dataset containing the highest daily values for BTC. Then the final test set was chosen as the last 300 consecutive days, and was removed from the data. The rest of the data (feature matrix and label vector) was then and split randomly to training and validation data. After processing there are 2643 datapoints altogether, of which 1640 are training datapoints, 703 are validation datapoints and 300 are test points.

In this project two different ML-models from Scikit-learn library are used; Linear regressor and Random Forest Regressor. Approaching the problem using a linear regression model assumes the linearity between the feature values and the labels, in this case the values of Bitcoin and Nasdaq at days d and $d + 1$. The advantage of this is that the calculations become much easier and there is no risk of over fitting with a high variance dataset, such as the value of Bitcoin. Linear regression calculates coefficients for linear combination of the given features to predict the label. The method solves the best best fitting function from the following hypothesis space:

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{linear}}^{(n=12)} := \left\{ h : \mathbb{R}^{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid h(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} \right\}.$$

Here \mathbf{x} is the feature vector and \mathbf{w} are the unknown coefficients. The other method used is the Random Forest Regressor. This method splits the data randomly into multiple decision trees and takes the average of every prediction. Each decision tree finds a split within each feature value that gives the most amount of information on predicting the label value. Decision forest regression was chosen as it does not assume the linearity between features and labels, and is not prone to over fitting, since it averages out each prediction from individual trees. The hypothesis space for the random tree regression model is more abstract and complex than with linear regression. It includes all the possible decision tree/forest configurations for the given feature and label data.

Both regression models use mean squared error as the loss function. Squared error loss has many advantages, such as computational efficiency (with finding the minima) and being easy to implement. It is the built in loss-function of the Sklearn LinearRegression-class and also used by default in the RandomForest-class. [3].

For linear regression the loss function is:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{12}} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left(y^{(i)} - \left(w_0 + w_1 x_1^{(i)} + w_2 x_2^{(i)} + \dots + w_{12} x_{12}^{(i)} \right) \right)^2$$

where $\mathbf{w} = [w_0 \ w_1 \ \dots \ w_{12}]$ are the parameters to be learned and $\mathbf{x} = [x_0 \ x_1 \ \dots \ x_{12}]$ the feature values [4].

For random tree regression the loss function is:

$$\min \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2$$

where y_i is the target value and \hat{y} is the predicted value.

The data was split between a training and validation set and a test set by removing the test set. The remaining data was then cut into training and validation with a 70/30-split. This split ensures that there are enough data points for training, while leaving enough data to be used for independent validation. It is also important that there are more training data points than validation data points. The data is split randomly so that any long term biases, such as economic trends, do not affect the model. The last 300 elements are reserved for testing, which represent the last 300 days in order (not chosen randomly). This is to make sure that there are no testing points from the time period of the validation and the training set. This also enables us to plot the models performance in a continuous manner.

4 Results

Unlike the linear regression model, the random forest regression model was trained on the training data for several times with varying values for the number of estimators and the maximum tree depth. Generally, increasing the number of estimators beyond 16 did not improve validation error. Similarly, having a max depth beyond 6 did not prove to be anymore beneficial for the validation error. Based on these tests, the value 16 was picked for the number of estimators and the maximum depth was set to 6. Although the validation errors did not increase significantly after these points, these values were still chosen to keep the model as simple as possible and to prevent possible overfitting.

The training and validation errors were determined with mean squared error (MSE), since both models were trained with a squared error loss function. For the training, the errors were 225481 (USD²) and 107841 (USD²) for the linear model and random forest respectively. The validation error for the linear model was around 216 602 (USD²) and for the random forest model the error was 249 843 (USD²). In addition the R^2 -scores[5] of the models were calculated from the validation data. R^2 -score closer to 1 indicates a more accurate model. The R^2 -scores were around 0.998321 for the linear model and 0.999197 for the random forest in training. In validation the scores were around 0.998186 and 0.997908 for the linear model and random forest model respectively.

Based on these results the linear regression model performed better slightly better in validation and was thus chosen as the final machine learning model for task. Applying

the learned model to the testing set resulted in a MSE of 1 786 698 (USD²) and a R^2 -score of around 0.978774. The behaviour of the model was visualised on the test set by plotting the values predicted by the model in the test set with the actual label values (Appendix A). From there it can be seen that the model is able to follow the market values approximately, but usually with a delay. Additionally, the model predictions are conservative and lack the capability to predict any large jumps in value.

5 Conclusion

Even though the both of the models can seemingly follow the price development with the validation data, they cannot accurately predict the value nor the value change one day ahead. The model's apparent accuracy can be explained by the calculated coefficients in the linear model, which show a strong bias toward the previous day's highest price. As a result, each prediction is heavily influenced by this feature, causing the model to predict values close to the previous day's high, while other features have a relatively smaller impact. This makes the model consistently lag behind by approximately one day in following price trends.

However, the chosen linear regression model was still able to predict whether the value will rise or fall within the next day 59.2% of the time in the test set. Consequently the expected value of the model on the 300 day test set is positive, at 0.7% return on investment. However the calculated EV-assumes that the investment is always realized at the maximum value of each day, so the actual value gain is most likely much smaller. Given the high volatility and theoretical winnings, this result shows that the model doesn't provide significant investment help, if any. Moreover Bitcoin as any financial instrument has the tendency to rise or fall slowly over a long time period, and the calculated ROI (using the model) is lower than the average value gain over the test period.

As with any financial instrument the value of Bitcoin is very hard to predict on a short time span. Bitcoin has a very high volatility, and the occurrence of large value spikes doesn't seem correlate with the chosen features. Over a longer time period these spikes even out, which is reflected on the model by predicting much more conservative value changes compared to reality.

In conclusion, despite having a high apparent accuracy according to the calculated machine learning metrics, the model doesn't work in the context of Bitcoin investing, where very small differences can have a large impact. The limitations of the model are mainly explained by the fact that the chosen features don't correlate with short term changes in the value of Bitcoin. The model could be improved by having more correlating features and concentrating on the changes of value rather than absolute value.

References

- [1] *Bitcoin Historical Data Set*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/prasoonkottarathil/btcinUSD>.
- [2] *Nasdaq Composite Index (COMP) Data Set*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nasdaq.com/market-activity/index/comp>.
- [3] *Scikit-learn.org LinearRegression*. [Online]. Available: https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.linear_model.LinearRegression.html.
- [4] A. Jung, *Machine Learning: The Basics*. Springer, Singapore 2022, ch. 3.2. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/alexjungaalto/MachineLearningTheBasics/blob/master/MLBasicsBook.pdf>.
- [5] *Scikit-learn.org, Metrics and scoring: quantifying the quality of predictions*. [Online]. Available: https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/model_evaluation.html#r2-score.

A Visualisation of the linear model

Figure 1: Linear regression models predictions for the daily high vales and the actual BTC daily highs on the test set.

Figure 2: The predicted change in the daily high values by the linear model, and the actual change in values.

mlearn

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```
[1]: # Import useful libraries
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
import sklearn.metrics as metrics
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor

[2]: # Loading the data into dataframes
btc = pd.read_csv('BTC-Daily.csv')
nasdaq = pd.read_csv('HistoricalData_1726755082831.csv')

# Dropping irrelevant columns
btc.drop(columns=['unix', 'symbol', 'close', 'Volume USD'], inplace=True)

# Renaming columns
btc.columns = ['date', 'open', 'high', 'low', 'volume btc']
nasdaq.columns = ['date', 'close', 'open', 'high', 'low']

[3]: # The dates are converted to the same format
btc['date'] = pd.to_datetime(btc['date']).dt.date
btc['date'] = pd.to_datetime(btc['date'])
nasdaq['date'] = pd.to_datetime(nasdaq['date'])

[4]: # Make the indexing chronological.
btc = btc[::-1].reset_index(drop=True)
nasdaq = nasdaq[::-1].reset_index(drop=True)

[5]: # Trimming the dataset to include only data from the same time period.
nasdaq.drop( nasdaq[nasdaq['date'] < btc['date'][0]].index, inplace=True )
nasdaq.drop( nasdaq[nasdaq['date'] > btc['date'].iloc[-1]].index, inplace=True )

[6]: # Nasdaq is closed on weekends, so our data set doesn't contain any information.
↳ for
```

```

# those days. We assume that the market value during the weekend
# is the same as the closing value of friday,
# and extend that for the missing dates.

new_rows = [] # List for the updated nasdaq data.
j = 0 # Indexing variable for looping through the original data.

# Iterate through every date in the btc dataframe and check for
# missing dates in nasdaq. If a date is missing, it
# is added to the list of new nasdaq data with the closing values from
# the previous recorded nasdaq date.
for i in range(len(btc)):
    if nasdaq['date'].iloc[j] == btc['date'].iloc[i]:
        row = [btc['date'].iloc[i], nasdaq['close'].iloc[j], nasdaq['open'].
        ↪iloc[j],
                nasdaq['high'].iloc[j], nasdaq['low'].iloc[j]]
        new_rows.append(row)
        j+=1
    else:
        close = nasdaq['close'].iloc[j-1]
        row = [btc['date'].iloc[i], close, close, close, close]
        new_rows.append(row)

# Create a new dataframe using the collected data.
new_nasdaq = pd.DataFrame(new_rows, columns=['date', 'close', 'open', 'high',
        ↪'low'])

# In the original nasdaq data, only the closing value is marked for holidays.
# Here that value is extended for the opening, high and low values also.
for i in range(len(new_nasdaq)):
    n_open = new_nasdaq['open'].iloc[i]
    n_high = new_nasdaq['high'].iloc[i]
    n_low = new_nasdaq['low'].iloc[i]
    if n_open == 0 and n_high == 0 and n_low == 0:
        close = new_nasdaq['close'].iloc[i]
        new_nasdaq.at[i, 'open'] = close
        new_nasdaq.at[i, 'high'] = close
        new_nasdaq.at[i, 'low'] = close

```

```

[7]: # Collect the change of the opening value in the last 7 days
# and in the last 3 days.
btc_week_change = []
btc_3day_change = []
nasdaq_week_change = []
nasdaq_3day_change = []
for i in range(7, len( btc['open'] )-1):
    btc_week_change.append( btc['open'].iloc[i]-btc['open'].iloc[i-7] )

```

```

    btc_3day_change.append( btc['open'].iloc[i]-btc['open'].iloc[i-3] )
    nasdaq_week_change.append( new_nasdaq['open'].iloc[i]-new_nasdaq['open'].
↪iloc[i-7] )
    nasdaq_3day_change.append( new_nasdaq['open'].iloc[i]-new_nasdaq['open'].
↪iloc[i-3] )

```

```

[8]: # Label values (highest value of BTC on day n)
y = btc['high'][8:].to_numpy()

# Feature values from the dataframes (day n-1)
x1 = btc[7:-1].drop(columns=['date']).to_numpy()
x2 = new_nasdaq[7:-1].drop(columns=['date']).to_numpy()

x3 = np.array(btc_week_change).reshape(-1,1)
x4 = np.array(btc_3day_change).reshape(-1,1)
x5 = np.array(nasdaq_week_change).reshape(-1,1)
x6 = np.array(nasdaq_3day_change).reshape(-1,1)

```

```

[9]: # Form the feature matrix
X = np.concatenate((x1,x2,x3,x4,x5,x6), axis=1)

# Amount of datapoint reserved for model visualisation
to_plot = 300 # round(len(y)*0.15)

# Let's reserve some data for plotting predictions (test set)
X_plot = X[-to_plot:,:]
y_plot = y[-to_plot:]

# Remove these points from the rest of data
X = X[:-to_plot, :]
y = y[:-to_plot]

# Splitting the data further to training data and validation data
X_train, X_val, y_train, y_val = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.3,
↪random_state=69)

# Finally we normalize the training data and validation data
# using the sklearn standard scaler
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_val_scaled = scaler.transform(X_val)
X_plot_scaled = scaler.transform(X_plot)

# Number of datapoints
print('Number of overall datapoints: ' + str(len(y)+len(y_plot)))
print('Number of training datapoints: ' + str(len(y_train)))
print('Number of validation datapoints: ' + str(len(y_val)))

```

```
print('Number of test set datapoints: ' + str(len(y_plot)))
```

Number of overall datapoints: 2643
Number of training datapoints: 1640
Number of validation datapoints: 703
Number of test set datapoints: 300

```
[10]: # Fitting a linear model on the training data
model1 = LinearRegression()
model1.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

# Calculating the training error
tr_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_train, model1.
    ↪predict(X_train_scaled))
tr_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_train, model1.predict(X_train_scaled))
print('Training error (MSE): ' + str(tr_error_mae))
print('Training R2 score: ' + str(tr_error_r2))

# Validation error of the model
val_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_val, model1.predict(X_val_scaled))
val_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_val, model1.predict(X_val_scaled))
print('Validation error (MSE): ' + str(val_error_mae))
print('Validation R2 score: ' + str(val_error_r2))
```

Training error (MSE): 225481.03717456272
Training R2 score: 0.9983209644468231
Validation error (MSE): 216602.2560274236
Validation R2 score: 0.9981864776342526

```
[11]: print('The coefficients of the linear model: \n' + str(model1.coef_))
```

The coefficients of the linear model:
[-4.41508640e+03 1.12303243e+04 4.72653901e+03 4.58005390e+01
 1.14130400e+03 -2.21599966e+02 -9.83080098e+02 9.55098939e+01
 3.77490164e+01 1.99687530e+00 -1.29725857e+00 -2.20969362e+01]

```
[12]: # Data visualisation from the test set:
# Plotting the BTC value and the model predictions
time = range(0, len(y_plot))
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(time, y_plot, label='BTC daily high', color='b')
plt.scatter(time, model1.predict(X_plot_scaled), label='Predicted daily high',
    ↪color='r')
plt.xlabel('Time in days')
plt.ylabel('USD')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Linear model')
```

```

test_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_plot, model1.
↳predict(X_plot_scaled))
test_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_plot, model1.predict(X_plot_scaled))
print('Testing error (MSE): ' + str(test_error_mae))
print('Testing R2 score: ' + str(test_error_r2))

```

Testing error (MSE): 1786697.7312701675

Testing R2 score: 0.9787748027492866


```

[13]: y1 = y_plot[1:] # Days from 1 to n
y2 = y_plot[:-1] # Day from 0 to n-1
diff = y1-y2 # Difference in daily highs
diff_pred = model1.predict(X_plot_scaled)[1:]-y2 # Predicted differences

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(range(1,len(y_plot)), diff_pred, color='r', label='Predicted change in_
↳daily high')
plt.plot(range(1,len(y_plot)), diff, color='b', label='Change in daily high_
↳compared to previous day')

```

```
plt.xlabel('Time in days')
plt.ylabel('USD')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Linear model')
```

```
[13]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'Linear model')
```



```
[14]: corr_pred = []
for i in range(0, len(diff)):
    corr_pred.append(np.sign(diff[i]) == np.sign(diff_pred[i]))
print('Percentage of correct predictions about the direction of value change: ' +
      ↪+
      str( round(100 * corr_pred.count(True) / len(corr_pred), 2)) + '%')
```

Percentage of correct predictions about the direction of value change: 59.2%

```
[15]: # Assume we bought BTC on every single day that our model predicts the value to
      ↪go up,
      # and then sold the BTC on the next day for the highest value of the day.
```

```

# We can now calculate the percentage of money earned during the observation
↳period.

earned = 0
used = 0
for i in range(0, len(diff_pred)):
    if diff_pred[i] > 0:
        earned += (y1[i]-y2[i])
        used += y2[i]
print('Percentage of money earned: ' + str(round(100*earned/used, 3)) + '%')

```

Percentage of money earned: 0.599%

```

[16]: # Fit a random forest model
model2 = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=16, criterion='squared_error',
↳random_state=69, max_depth=6)
model2.fit(X_train_scaled, y_train)

# Calculating the training error
tr_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_train, model2.
↳predict(X_train_scaled))
tr_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_train, model2.predict(X_train_scaled))
print('Training error (MSE): ' + str(tr_error_mae))
print('Training R2 score: ' + str(tr_error_r2))

# Validation error of the model
val_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_val, model2.predict(X_val_scaled))
val_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_val, model2.predict(X_val_scaled))
print('Validation error (MSE): ' + str(val_error_mae))
print('Validation R2 score: ' + str(val_error_r2))

```

Training error (MSE): 107848.78277241152
Training R2 score: 0.9991969083391188
Validation error (MSE): 249843.0596990632
Validation R2 score: 0.997908165939723

```

[17]: # Data visualisation from the test set:
# Plotting the BTC value and the model predictions
time = range(0, len(y_plot))
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(time, y_plot, label='BTC daily high', color='b')
plt.scatter(time, model2.predict(X_plot_scaled), label='Predicted daily high',
↳color='r')
plt.xlabel('Time in days')
plt.ylabel('USD')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Random forest model')

```

```

test_error_mae = metrics.mean_squared_error(y_plot, model2.
↳predict(X_plot_scaled))
test_error_r2 = metrics.r2_score(y_plot, model2.predict(X_plot_scaled))
print('Testing error (MSE): ' + str(test_error_mae))
print('Testing R2 score: ' + str(test_error_r2))

```

Testing error (MSE): 3633980.9327622573

Testing R2 score: 0.9568298762833392


```

[18]: y1 = y_plot[1:] # Days from 1 to n
y2 = y_plot[:-1] # Days from 0 to n-1
diff = y1-y2 # Difference in daily highs
diff_pred = model2.predict(X_plot_scaled)[1:]-y2 # Predicted difference

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(range(1,len(y_plot)), diff_pred, color='r', label='Predicted change in_
↳daily high')
plt.plot(range(1,len(y_plot)), diff, color='b', label='Change in daily high_
↳compared ot previous day')

```

```
plt.xlabel('Time in days')
plt.ylabel('USD')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Random forest model')
```

```
[18]: Text(0.5, 1.0, 'Random forest model')
```



```
[19]: corr_pred = []
for i in range(0, len(diff)):
    corr_pred.append(np.sign(diff[i]) == np.sign(diff_pred[i]))
print('Percentage of correct predictions about the direction of value change: ' +
      ↪+
      str( round(100 * corr_pred.count(True) / len(corr_pred), 2)) + '%')
```

Percentage of correct predictions about the direction of value change: 55.85%

```
[20]: # Assume we bought BTC on every single day that our model predicts the value to
      ↪go up,
      # and then sold the BTC on the next day for the highest value of the day.
```

```
# We can now calculate the percentage of money earned during the observation  
↳ period.  
  
earned = 0  
used = 0  
for i in range(0, len(diff_pred)):  
    if diff_pred[i] > 0:  
        earned += (y1[i]-y2[i])  
        used += y2[i]  
print('Percentage of money earned: ' + str(round(100*earned/used, 3)) + '%')
```

Percentage of money earned: 0.316%